

NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRENDS IN WORD FORMATION (BASED ON TEXTS IN THE MEDIA)

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7765527>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th March 2023

Accepted: 23th March 2023

Online: 24th March 2023

KEY WORDS

The concept of Neologism, neologisms in Uzbek languages, the trend in Word formation and the role of neologisms in the media.

ABSTRACT

This article is about the concept of neologisms in English and Uzbek, and the concept of neologism in word-making, comparative analysis and trends of neologisms, which often appeared in the field of Medicine during the pandemic, as well as the communicative-pragmatic study of neologisms, an in-depth analysis of the ways in which new lexical elements.

In the first decade of the 21st century, humanity had many natural and artificial commands, epidemics, terrorist attacks and wars. All this was widely reported in their media over a period of time. At different times, the linguistic features of articles on the Wuhan epidemic, the fight against pneumonia, the swine flu, the Zika virus, and the Ebola epidemic have been at the center of research by linguists. In 2020, all countries have faced a global problem like the COVID-19 pandemic. COVID-19 has quickly risen among viral diseases, leaving behind seasonal influenza and tuberculosis.

N.M. Shansky neologism refers to a word in the language that “does not take place as a unit with a certain meaning from an active vocabulary Reserve. Such words will continue to be neologism until they fully assimilate and integrate into the active reserve of vocabulary content, eliminating the property of novelty and inadequacy.” Another group of researchers believes that neologisms come to the fore from the traditions of the language of the past. On the issue of the emergence of neologism, R.A. Budagov expresses the following opinion: “any new word is inextricably linked with the traditions of the past language... usually; new words appear on the basis of the internal capability of the language or as a result of mastering that is, taking a word from another language finally turning into related nouns.” E.V. Senko believes that the classification sign of neologism is associated with the degree of its novelty. On this basis, it identifies three types of neologism: the strong, the weak and the intermediate stage.

The disease has covered all countries of the world, led to unprecedented quarantine measures, and the heads of states assessed it as “the greatest catastrophe in history” (USA), “the most serious call since World War II” (GFR), “the World War III” (France). The issue of economic evaluation and disposal of the social consequences of the pandemic were presented to the global community. In the way COVID-19 has become a major innovation for the world leader average. Information about this disease was provided on all open information

platforms, including blogs, YouTube, Twitter, regional and central media, speeches of local politicians and heads of state. The leaders of Russia, Great Britain, Germany, France, the United States, Uzbekistan and other countries regularly spoke to their citizens. Special tests for coronavirus have been prepared; information was provided through the media websites, bookmarks and mobile apps have been created. Excessive expansion of the information space sometimes led to the fact that sometimes the desire to read publications on this topic, see and hear news disappeared altogether. Therefore, in practice, the extent of public approval of this issue did not leave anyone behind in the information field.

In 2020-2022, the active application that appeared due to the spread of the COVID-19 virus is associated with the need to be interested in acquiring new words. This is of particular interest to neologisms, because they express society's attitude to the rapidly changing realities of the language owners' lives. New words appearing in the linguistic system are usually coined from the term neologisms. The question of understanding neologism is determined by the fact that the approach to the study of this term is different. In neology, new words are interpreted as neologism, occasionalism, new name, lexical innovation, etc. Russian linguists understand the essence of neologism in different ways. The interpretation of this concept is narrow and broad. To a first approximation, neologism is understood as words that serve as the name of a new thing, phenomenon and concepts. A.V. Kalinin believes that a neologism is a word that appeared as a result of the development of science, technology, culture, agriculture, new social relations, as well as performing the task of naming new things, phenomena and concepts. It is "not just a new word, but a completely new word that appeared in the coming days, the freshness of which is clearly noticeable to the language's owners." A.G. Likov believes that it is necessary to understand of a new word in the language, the first stage of its historical activity in the language.

Studying the process of application of Anglicism in the oral speech of the Russian language, E.V. Larionova proposes to divide words into speech perceptions and speech spreads, based on the fact that speech spreads are associated with the speech skills of bilingual language owners, with the need for language owners and Ridge. A.B. Akhmedov described neologism as follows: "by neologism we understand new words, word meanings and expressions that are new in form and content, appeared at a certain time of language development, were generally taken by language owners and acquired commonality, were perceived as new during this period, meet the norms of language". Lexical groups over time related to the names of the new Relays are separated in the language system. In the current period, neologisms are divided by type's linguistic unit, degree of novelty, duration of the question:

1) Words that appear in the process of word formation and word change from new languages;

2) New phraseology and new phraseology consisting of stable compounds;

3) New words representing the new meaning formed in the old word and phraseology.

According to the degree of novelty, neologisms are divided into the following types:

1) Words and phraseology that were not previously in the linguistic system are absolute new creations;

2) Relative neologisms representing ancient realities.

E.A.Zemskaya believes that neologisms are often created in order to represent one or another phenomenon in existence, and also indicate the degree of importance of these phenomena.

In this respect, they differ from absolute neologisms. There are the following types of relative neologisms: lexicon, activated lexicon, internal assimilations, which are again adapted in the linguistic system. Re-application the acquired lexicon is understood as "words that have been activated in their new life, while retaining the old meaning and functional-methodological function". What happened in society is a lexicon, in connection with events of which a new meaning is activated. Internal pronouns refer to words and phrases derived from colloquial speech, various branches of Science and technology, jargon, dialects into the literary language. As an example of internal assimilation neologisms, one can cite the terms medicine: SPID, covid and others. According to the duration of application, neologisms are distinguished that are used once, are used in the language system for a long time and are applied for a short time, and then go out of consumption. Traditional classification of neologisms D.E.Rosenthal, N.M.Shansky and K.S.Gorbachev noted in his work. They classified neologisms into the following types:

1) Lexical neologisms made on the basis of existing word-making patterns in a language or borrowed from other languages. Neologisms in this group are made on the basis of such common word-making molds as suffixing, prefixing, prefixing-suffixing, abbreviation.

2) Semantic neologisms, pre-existing in the language, which have a new meaning as a result of the changes existing in the keying period.

The research materials were collected using a language body from journalistic texts and colloquial speech and dictionaries. Neologisms classified on the basis of the attitude of language owners to coronavirus are divided into the following lexical semantic groups:

- Neologisms that represent the social processes taking place in the life of society;
- Neologisms that represent the community of people;
- Neologisms that represent the form of work and education;
- Neologisms that represent the subjects related to the disease.

In my conclusion I will add to the opinion expressed by Zemskaya because it is neologisms, which often shed light on its creation with the aim of expressing this or that phenomenon in being. Coronavirus infection and pandemic strongly influenced the usual way of life of people, which led to a change in social processes. For example, in English, the neologism "elbow bump" appeared which has the meaning of elbow touch as a greeting sign. The spread of infection by airborne droplets, direct contacts such as shaking hands, as well as the observance of etiquette led to the emergence of a new form of greeting, the formation of a new vocabulary that, in accordance with this, represents it. In Uzbek society, too, it was forbidden to shake hands during this period, and people saw their elbows, or their exhausted fists fighting, and switched to a vision that was characteristic of our people for a long time, keeping a distance by placing the hand on the chest. However, no special new word or phrase was created that represented this meaning. This lexical group also includes the lockdown neologism, which appeared in English. According to the British national corps, this word was first used in 1973 in the sense of temporarily holding a prisoner in a prison cell as a security measure, taking into account the occurrence of a threat.

References:

1. Akhmanova O.S. Slovarlingvitecheskikh terminov. Izd.4-ye, stereotipnaye. M.: KomKniga, 2007. - 567 b.
2. Akhmedov A.B. On the linguistic status of neologism / / Foreign philology: language, literature, education. - №3 (84), 2022. – B. 33-37.
3. Bugadov R.A. Slovo I yegoznachenije: Nauch.- papul.ocher.L.: izd. Type I. Izd-and Leningr.gos.ardenaleninaun-ta, 1947. - 66 b.
4. Golotova T.A. Metaphorization virus Zika v rossiyskikhelektronnixizdaniyax: kognitivno-diskursivny aspect / T.A.Golotova, O.G.Krivova, N.A.Kulbachenko / / Philologicheskienauki. The theory of vaprasi I praktiki. – 2016. - № 11-2 (65). – B.51-56.
5. Zemskaya Ye. A. Aktivniyeprotsesisovremennogoslovoproizvodstva / / Russkiyyazikkonsa XX stoletiyasa. - M., 1996. – B. 90-141.
6. Kasimova A.N. “Translation methods and techniques publicistic materials”.-B.40
7. Kasimova A.N.“Motivationandawarenessinpractice”
8. bosma 2017, SamDJTI, “Xorijiyfilologiya: til, aadabiyot, ta’lim” .
9. Kasimova A.N.“The roleandinfluenceofmass madiainteachingEnglish”bosma 2018, SamDJTI, “Xorijiyfilologiya: til, adabiyot, ta’lim”, 4(69) 5, 6-9 .
10. Kasimova A.N.“Modern methodsof teachingtotranslationofpublicistic texts”bosma 2021, SamDJTI, “Xorijiyfilologiya: til, aadabiyot, ta’lim”, (nashrda)
11. Kasimova A.N.“Translation methodsandtechniques ofpublicisticmaterials”bosma7.03.2022 Kasimova A.N. So’zsan’ati, №5 (3),
12. www.ziyo.net
13. www.ziyo.uz
14. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=gzNd2u0AAA AJ&citation_for_view=gzNd2u0AAAAJ:9yKSN-GCB0IC
15. [https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=ru&user=gzNd2u0AAAAJ#:~:text=NEWSPAPER %20STYLE.%20THE,2](https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=ru&user=gzNd2u0AAAAJ#:~:text=NEWSPAPER%20STYLE.%20THE,2)
16. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=gzNd2u0AAA AJ&citation_for_view=gzNd2u0AAAAJ:zYLM7Y9cAGgC
17. NEWSPAPER STYLE. THE TRANSLATION ISSUES OF LEXICAL UNITS AND WORD COMBINATIONS IN NEWSPAPER TEXTS KA Nosirovna Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10 (2), 285-287